

Stage 1: Interview Question Guide

For Stage 1 of the semi-structured interview study reported in the paper "What You See is What You Trace - A Two-Stage Interview Study on Traceability Practices and Eye Tracking Potential"

Introduction and Background

1. Introduction of the interviewer: briefly explain content and structure of the interview, anonymous analysis of responses and right to cancel or request data deletion at any time
2. Do you agree with this interview being recorded?
3. Please describe your role and tasks concerning software projects.
4. How long (in years) have you been working in or with software projects?
5. How many people work in the projects that you work on? Average, Min, Max
6. How long is the runtime of projects on which you work on usually? Average, Min, Max
7. Which development process is primarily used in those software projects? Agile, traditional, hybrid?
 - a. Is there a dedicated requirements elicitation or documentation phase?
 - b. If so, how long is this phase?
8. How security-critical or safety-critical are the projects on which you usually work on? Are people at risk or sensitive sets of data involved?

Part 1: Requirements Management

9. Which artifact types are used in your projects? (e.g., textual requirements, models, UML, user stories, project plan, code, tests, etc.)
10. How are requirements documented in the projects on which you usually work on?
 - a. Are tools being used for this documentation?
 - b. Which applications are used to store and manage requirements?
11. Is there a specific "workflow" when you are working with requirements?
12. Which document types or artifacts are often used in parallel? I.e., one is accessed directly after the other or both are shown on the screen simultaneously.

Part 2: Traceability Practices, Benefits and Problems

13. Have you heard of tracing/ traceability? Are you aware what it means?
 - a. If not or unsure, give short explanation.
 - i. Software Traceability is defined as the ability to link together related artifacts from different sources within a project.
 - ii. Traceability of requirements is the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement in both a forwards and backwards direction.
 - iii. Its advantages include requirements coverage analysis, change impact analysis or dependency analysis.
 - b. If yes, how was tracing implemented in your projects?
 - i. In what way? What was traced? Were there different types of links? Which granularity?
 - ii. How much manual effort was required? Was it implemented for the entire project or only certain parts?
 - iii. How well did it work? Were there any problems?
 - iv. For what purpose did you use it?
14. What is your personal opinion regarding traceability? Do you think that the benefits outweigh the costs?

Part 3: Requirements for Automatic Tracing

15. If you pictured ideal traceability, i.e., anything could be linked with anything at no cost, which artifact types should ideally be linked in your opinion? (e.g., requirements and code, code and tests, design decisions and requirements, ...)
16. Which level of granularity should trace links have? (document level, paragraph level, sentence level)
17. Imagine yourself using a fully automatic approach for detecting trace links with an accuracy 100%. Which type of error do you think is worse for you? Detected links being incorrect (false positives) or correct links not being detected (false negatives)?

Part 4: Tracing with Eye Tracking

18. The next questions are asked in a more open way. For that I would like you to look at this slide explaining an approach to use eye tracking to support the automatic detection of trace links. The idea is that eye tracking data are automatically recorded while people – may it be requirements engineers, architects, developers or testers – normally work on their tasks. By unintrusively recording gaze data in the background, it can be detected which artifacts are often looked at consecutively. Thereby, links are being generated between those artifacts. This way, when looking at that artifact again you can directly access related ones by following these detected links. E.g., when you look at a JIRA ticket, then at a part of a specification page and then to another related document, this gaze path could be processed to trace links between those artifacts.
19. Do you have any questions about the approach? Did you understand the concept? Did anything remain unclear?
20. Generally speaking: what do you think of the approach? Do you see a use for it? Do you have any concerns?
21. Could you see yourself having an eye tracker running while you are working or would you have concerns regarding privacy and observation? Which preconditions would need to be fulfilled for you to feel comfortable with detecting trace links based on gaze data?
22. Do you think that it might make sense to collect links in a context-sensitive manner? I.e., that links depend on the person's role or the task that they were working on while the trace link was collected?

Conclusion

23. Is there anything you would like to add? Do you have any questions or remarks?
24. Would you be interested in receiving the results of the study by email?